

One Way Analysis of Variance

Data source: Data 1 in Blood glucose-peso Notebook1.JNB

Normality Test (Shapiro-Wilk): Failed (P < 0,050)

Equal Variance Test (Brown-Forsythe): Failed (P < 0,050)

Group Name	N	Missing	Mean	Std Dev	SEM
Control-5weeks	3	0	82,000	2,646	1,528
HI-5weeks	128	0	74,090	18,176	1,607
HG-5weeks	17	0	120,512	54,011	13,099
Control-7weeks	27	0	72,963	11,471	2,208
HI-7WEEKS	123	0	76,350	20,242	1,825
HG-7WEEKS	18	0	140,667	70,044	16,509
Control-15WEEKS	10	0	75,000	7,196	2,275
HI-15WEEKS	107	0	83,458	18,512	1,790
HG-15WEEKS	10	0	330,700	85,897	27,163

Source of Variation	DF	SS	MS	F	P
Between Groups	8	708263,088	88532,886	116,912	<0,001
Residual	434	328652,046	757,263		
Total	442	1036915,134			

The differences in the mean values among the treatment groups are greater than would be expected by chance; there is a statistically significant difference (P = <0,001).

Power of performed test with alpha = 0,050: 1,000

All Pairwise Multiple Comparison Procedures (Holm-Sidak method):

Overall significance level = 0,05

Comparisons for factor:

Comparison	Diff of Means	t	P	P<0,050
HG-15WEEKS vs. HI-5weeks	256,610	28,400	<0,001	Yes
HG-15WEEKS vs. HI-7WEEKS	254,350	28,108	<0,001	Yes
HG-15WEEKS vs. HI-15WEEKS	247,242	27,171	<0,001	Yes
HG-15WEEKS vs. Control-7weeks	257,737	25,301	<0,001	Yes
HG-15WEEKS vs. Control-15WEEKS	255,700	20,777	<0,001	Yes
HG-15WEEKS vs. HG-5weeks	210,188	19,166	<0,001	Yes
HG-15WEEKS vs. HG-7WEEKS	190,033	17,509	<0,001	Yes
HG-15WEEKS vs. Control-5weeks	248,700	13,729	<0,001	Yes
HG-7WEEKS vs. HI-5weeks	66,577	9,611	<0,001	Yes
HG-7WEEKS vs. HI-7WEEKS	64,317	9,262	<0,001	Yes
HG-7WEEKS vs. HI-15WEEKS	57,209	8,160	<0,001	Yes
HG-7WEEKS vs. Control-7weeks	67,704	8,085	<0,001	Yes
HG-5weeks vs. HI-5weeks	46,422	6,535	<0,001	Yes
HG-5weeks vs. HI-7WEEKS	44,162	6,202	<0,001	Yes
HG-7WEEKS vs. Control-15WEEKS	65,667	6,050	<0,001	Yes
HG-5weeks vs. Control-7weeks	47,549	5,581	<0,001	Yes
HG-5weeks vs. HI-15WEEKS	37,054	5,157	<0,001	Yes
HG-5weeks vs. Control-15WEEKS	45,512	4,150	<0,001	Yes
HG-7WEEKS vs. Control-5weeks	58,667	3,419	0,012	Yes
HI-15WEEKS vs. HI-5weeks	9,368	2,599	0,152	No
HG-5weeks vs. Control-5weeks	38,512	2,235	0,343	No
HG-7WEEKS vs. HG-5weeks	20,155	2,166	0,375	No
HI-15WEEKS vs. HI-7WEEKS	7,108	1,954	0,522	No
HI-15WEEKS vs. Control-7weeks	10,495	1,771	0,649	No
HI-15WEEKS vs. Control-15WEEKS	8,458	0,929	0,995	No

HI-7WEEKS vs. HI-5weeks	2,260	0,650	1,000	No
HI-7WEEKS vs. Control-7weeks	3,387	0,579	1,000	No
Control-5wee vs. Control-7wee	9,037	0,540	1,000	No
Control-5weeks vs. HI-5weeks	7,910	0,492	1,000	No
Control-5wee vs. Control-15WE	7,000	0,386	1,000	No
Control-5weeks vs. HI-7WEEKS	5,650	0,351	1,000	No
Control-15WE vs. Control-7wee	2,037	0,200	1,000	No
HI-5weeks vs. Control-7weeks	1,127	0,193	0,999	No
HI-7WEEKS vs. Control-15WEEKS	1,350	0,149	0,998	No
Control-15WEEKS vs. HI-5weeks	0,910	0,101	0,994	No
HI-15WEEKS vs. Control-5weeks	1,458	0,0905	0,928	No